

**The Complementarity of Legal Data Platforms: Identification
of Functionalities and Open Issues**

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The Complementarity of Legal Data Platforms: Identification of Functionalities and Open Issues

Abstract

Legal informatics based on legal data sources is expected to bring many advantages for the community, legislative procedure and policy making. To support the provision and use of legal data and to stimulate the realization of these advantages, a variety of legal data artefacts and portals, both proprietary and open, has been created and is currently under development. The release of these legal data platforms raises the question how they complement and relate to each other in terms of basic services they provide and the use of semantic assets for data description towards the support of more advanced services. There is no systematic analysis of these platforms. In this study a framework for comparing legal data infrastructures is derived and used to compare seven different legal data sources and portals across the EU. The comparison shows that legal data sources and associated portals can be very diverse in terms of sophistication and focus resulting in different design choices, with each infrastructure demonstrating its own specific strengths. We argue that these legal data sources as well as the capabilities they offer could complement each other towards the provision of a united EU legal data system utilising and in turn providing open interfaces. In this way an open legal data ecosystem would be shaped in which the best added-value services and functionalities could be utilized with the provision and use of open legal data and the realization of their advantages being stimulated.

1. Introduction

Legal information is one of the most important sources of open data in our society. Policy makers, legal experts and professionals, parliamentary staff, but also businesses and citizens are some of the user groups that are constantly interested in this type of information. However, different categories of users possess differing informational needs (Virkar et. al., 2020b), and hence, legal information systems have to provide a variety of functionalities. Possibly the most basic among these is the ability to easily search for and find the legal information and/or the relevant fragments necessary to build a legal case or to remain informed about specific phenomena (Virkar, 2020a). Legal information is open by default, but in most of the cases in a very restricted and non machine-processable format like .pdf making it hard for the users to identify a necessary part of information. Users are often confronted with the challenge of accessing vast, hitherto untapped, sources of legal information in an efficient manner that not only provides them with all relevant information, but also assists and supports them substantially in day-to-day tasks (Charalabidis et. al., 2019). This difficulty is exacerbated by the fact that national gazettes publish information on multiple legal issues at the same time.

Furthermore, recent trends in digitization, open data, and social media have resulted in an exponential increase in the amount of data available for use by policy makers in order to make sense of the socio-economic and political phenomena, and design relevant public policies (Alexopoulos et. al. 2020). The increased availability of legal data also enables citizens to stay informed about

current policy trends and allows them to participate in public consultations (Julieta Lugo-Gil, et al., 2019). Repositories of large quantities of novel types of information – including expert knowledge, sensor data, text, social media posts - have become available to all stakeholders. The new paradigm targets the integration of all the necessary types of information towards more data-driven decision making. Furthermore, accurate and timely legal information is an essential component of effective decision-making by several different societal actors (Virkar et. al, 2019). However, the ability of citizens, businesses, public servants as well as politicians and their advisers to easily access, fully comprehend and apply complex legal information to their everyday contexts often hinges on an advanced understanding of governmental procedures, legal language, and the law itself (Virkar et. al., 2020b). Unfortunately, usually this does not always happen, and most people struggle and have difficulties to locate the legal artefacts they need.

In any case, full-text legal databases have, since the mid-1980s, increasingly become the primary and most significant source of information for all stakeholders concerning existing or previous relevant legislation, for their home country as well as other countries (Berring, 1986). Advanced intelligent systems, together with sophisticated techniques of data harvesting, annotation, analysis and visualisation have enhanced our ability to understand and make sense of extensive and complex relevant information (Endert et. al., 2017). However, research that has been conducted in the area of legal informatics often concerns its ‘supply side’, dealing with the development of effective systems for legal information provision, with advanced search and processing capabilities, based on appropriate metadata as well as organization and annotation of large quantities of textual legal information (Alexopoulos et. al. 2020). The flip-side of this is that only limited research has been conducted on the ‘demand side’ of legal information provision, though it is absolutely necessary to gain a good understanding of current trends in order to support the ecosystem of legal information.

This study aims at the comprehensive analysis of the functionality and the offered capabilities of legal information platforms to support users’ objectives and thus to also cover the demand side of legal information. An analysis framework has been created towards the identification of different functionalities. Behind the term functionality, we included all necessary features of open data as well as specific features of legal information and data. The major objective is to unveil if and how legal data platforms complement each other towards the development of a European legal data solution that allows for exchange of legal information for all member states and support the demand side. Specific aspects of national legal systems are also analysed: Legal Base Unit (an official gazette issue or other more sophisticated types of legal information provision originating from information systems); types and kinds of data offered; the technologies behind the provided functionality; interoperability standard used and ontological approaches followed; services provided to the final users supporting the development of an ecosystem (such as capabilities to request for data, or the provision of public opinion metrics) as well as the language support.

The paper is structured as follows: section 2 provides the background research in the area of legal informatics, interoperability and types of legal data. Section 3 presents the methodological approach and the analysis framework. Section 4 includes the results of the study on the analysed platforms. Section 5 provides a discussion regarding the different aspects of user groups and finally section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Related Research

2.1 Legal Informatics

“*Legal Informatics*” refers to the scholarly discipline which deals with the application of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) to the processing of legal information, and the provision of support to legal activities within the context of the legal environment (Biasiotti et. al., 2008; Erdelez, O'Hare, 1997). Sartor & Francesconi (2010) define the term as the “...*theory and practice of computable law, i.e. the cooperation between humans and machines in legal problem-solving*”. This area of study focuses on the opportunities and challenges arising through the implementation of advanced ICT within the legal system, and thus encompasses the activities of all related organizations and legal information users in the legal domain (Hinson, 2005). Of particular concern is the provision of relevant legal services, which are currently under-consumed by individuals and companies, through the development of usable legal information systems and software (Hornsby, 1999). Hence, the latest advancements in legal informatics are targeted towards making services more open and promoting access to legal resources (Ronkainen, 2012). In terms of scope, Legal Informatics has the potential to be an elementary part of both government (GovTech) and legal technology (LegalTech), and possesses the latent ability to transform entire parts of the public sector (Dawes et al., 2009). Thus, it is an interdisciplinary field integrating law and information science maintaining particular links with the semantic web (Sartor et al., 2011).

A recent, important trend in the area of legal informatics involves the increased exploitation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies, resulting in the emergence of new legal applications based on text and natural language processing and machine learning that appear to influence significantly - and aim to gradually transform - the practice of the law (Ashley, 2017). These tools and services support both advanced legal information retrieval and predictive legal analysis by connecting computational models of legal reasoning directly with legal text (Alexopoulos et. al., 2020). Virkar et. al. (2020a), in paraphrasing (Moens, 2001), argues that the legal field remains one of the most difficult domains for the application of automated text retrieval, as legal text retrieval is based primarily upon concepts, and not on the explicit wording in the document texts. Casanovas (2016) argues that this is because legal concepts are not discrete, but instead are situated along “...a dynamic continuum between common sense terms, specific technical use, and professional knowledge, in an evolving institutional reality.” Moreover, Schweighofer (1997) notes, legal text retrieval has traditionally relied upon external knowledge sources such as thesauri and classification schemes, and the manual indexing of documents.

A constant research stream that could be included in the functional analysis is the one that investigates decision support. The term ‘decision support system’ (or DSS) represents a conceptualisation of the role played by information technology and associated applications in supporting long-term, sustainable decision-making (Virkar et. al., 2020b). An early definition of these systems identifies their design and subsequent development as involving the application of computers to improve managerial decision making in semi-structured and unstructured tasks, providing support as against replacing managerial judgement, and impacting the effectiveness of decisions rather than their efficiency (Keen & Scott Morton, 1978). As technology has increased in

sophistication, the term DSS has come to encompass not just the hardware involved in the automation of decision-making processes, but also the software applications and services that focus on supporting human cognitive reasoning (Watson, 2017).

Reliable information is a fundamental requirement for effective decision-making (Virkar et. al., 2020b). Various types of DSS facilitate the use and manipulation of very large databases (Powers, 1997). Of these, document-driven DSS have their roots in the field of bibliographic information retrieval, which facilitate the systematic searching and sorting of large quantities of information within textual databases through the application of advanced document management techniques (Sprague & Watson, 1996). In keeping with recent trends, cognitive modelling and AI techniques are now incorporated into expert information retrieval systems to produce advanced Document-driven DSS based on targeted user experiences (Bartolozzi et al., 2015). Many legal information retrieval systems could be characterised as Document-driven DSS since they include the retrieval of information from structured and unstructured texts and databases, the translation of text, and the semantic annotation of the obtained information (Virkar et. al., 2020b).

2.2 Interoperability and Standards

In terms of interoperability there are a lot of standards and editing tools to support legal drafting (Loutsaris & Charalabidis, 2020). The most known three metadata standards are being used to describe legal documents:

- Akoma Ntoso--defines a set of simple, technology-neutral electronic representations of parliamentary, legislative and judiciary documents for e-services in a worldwide context and provides an enabling framework for the effective exchange of “machine readable” parliamentary, legislative and judiciary documents such as legislation, debate record, minutes, judgements, etc.
- ELI-> European Law Institute (ELI) is an independent non-profit organisation established to initiate, conduct and facilitate research, make recommendations and provide practical guidance in the field of European legal development with a goal of enhancing the European legal integration. The idea of an ELI was inspired by the activities of the American Law Institute (ALI), founded in 1923 and headquartered in Philadelphia, Pennsylvania.
- DCAT-->Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) is an RDF vocabulary designed to facilitate interoperability between data catalogs published on the Web. By using DCAT to describe datasets in catalogs, publishers increase discoverability and enable applications to consume metadata from multiple catalogs. It enables decentralized publishing of catalogs and facilitates federated dataset search across catalogs. Aggregated DCAT metadata can serve as a manifest file to facilitate digital preservation.

On the other hand, LEOS is an open source software offering the possibility of wide configuration, which in turn makes it a powerful authoring tool for public administrations. LEOS and all the editing tools that are compatible with one of the basic ontologies constitute a way to ensure interoperability-by-design in the description and drafting of legal information. LEOS allows for the design of predefined AKN-compatible templates for each category of legal document, such as draft laws, draft presidential decrees, draft ministerial decisions and, in the context of this article, parliamentary questions (LEOS, 2020).

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3 Finally, legal data are by default open and should be published under the open data regime.
4 Although legal information is generally considered at the core of the open data movement and a
5 major part of public sector information, the legal framework of each member state, as well as the
6 European Parliament regulations, directives or directions are not accessible through the European
7 Data Portal (EDP). The Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) [Data Catalog Vocabulary, 2019] could
8 be used to transform legal data in open legal data following the open data process and include them
9 in the European Data Portal (EDP). DCAT is also a flat metadata schema for the creation of
10 vocabularies that includes datasets. As datasets, in the case of legal information, could be
11 considered the XML representation of the legal texts.

12 13 **2.3 Types of Legal data**

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15 In general, legal information is contained in documents that are stored in document databases. This
16 specific type of information is text and reading connected with appropriate visualisation and editing
17 techniques is necessary for all the user groups. The new paradigm characterises them as big data
18 (based on further analysis and creation of n-grams, correlations and translations) and as linked data
19 following the existing ontological approaches.

20 The large amount of information about laws that apply in the EU countries currently remains
21 fragmented across multiple national databases, inaccessible systems, mainly consisting of
22 documents published in each Member States' language. The types of legislative documents are:
23 acts, bills, case laws, resolutions, decisions, court decisions, directives; and they are forming the
24 different types of legal data. In most of the cases this information is provided by different platforms
25 dedicated to a specific type of legal data. This is because of the structural specificities in each type
26 of legal information document.

27 In an effort to categorise legal data types in the EU (Alexopoulos et al., 2020), there are 3 major
28 categories: (a) primary legal data (directives and regulations at the EU level, and laws, local laws
29 (when the legal system of a country allows for it), presidential decrees and ministerial decisions at
30 the national level); (b) court decisions (case laws) and (c) parliamentary data including pre-bills,
31 bills and all accompanying documents.

32 33 34 **3. Methodology and Analysis Framework Development**

35 The objective of this research is to identify and analyse the functionalities of different platforms
36 (laws, bills, case laws) at different levels (EU, national) providing capabilities for legal data
37 processing and visualisation. The methodological approach is presented in the following Figure 1. It
38 consists of 4 steps.

- 39
40 1. Identification of platforms providing legal data and services. The criteria used for the
41 selection were:
 - 42 a. Include both proprietary and non-proprietary platforms;
 - 43 b. Include all levels (national and European) and types (laws, bills, case law) of legal
44 data;
 - 45 c. Include ongoing research results.
- 46 2. Composition of the Analysis Framework. This step includes the specification of the analysis
47 aspects. In this research, open legal data platforms could be perceived as a product. Even
48 though a lot of research has already been done producing remarkable results, it seems that
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new applications and use of open legal data might result in new insights which might result in new functionality and ways of dealing with open legal data. Legal Data are examined as a specific type of open data that are created, published, found, used, linked, reused and discussed. These aspects of the process produce different requirements for legal open data platforms. In general, Open data infrastructures could offer mechanisms that enable sharing, exchanging and reusing data. Zuiderwijk et al. (2013) categorized requirements for the open data process into twelve categories: 1) access, 2) searching, 3) navigation, 4) uploading, 5) downloading, 6) data quality, 7) analysis of datasets, 8) visualization, 9) linking and combining data, 10) collaboration, 11) support and help and 12) feedback. In addition, Alexopoulos et al. (2018) provided an analysis framework towards thorough analysis of the thematic, functional, semantic and technological characteristics of open data. We concluded our final framework through the combination of the above frameworks. Some extra indicators have been added in order to cover specific aspects of legal data (e.g. national legal system). The description of each indicator/element of the analysis framework is presented in Table 1.

Figure 1: Methodological Approach

- Analysis of the selected platforms. The authors of this paper are researchers working in the field of legal data and can be considered as experts in the legal informatics domain either as users or as developers of such solutions. All the platforms have been tested and analysed in national and EU contexts. When fees for accessing the platforms occurred, they were covered from annual subscriptions of the authors. For each functionality that was evaluated, possible answers were listed and a number of criteria were created. A discussion among the authors took place to select the right answer.
- Presentation of Results. This step includes the description of the analysis results in step 3, as well as the synthesis of functionalities (complementarity) towards the creation of an open legal data ecosystem. Furthermore, we discuss the open issues in each level of the analysis in order to better support the realisation of the ecosystem and the European approach.

Table 1: Indicators of the Analysis Framework

Indicator	Description
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General	Type of Information, Access, Coverage, data level, Legal System, data type, data format, URL
Data Acquisition	Data acquisition mechanism (e.g. API) available, connecting to the primary source. Uploading information relies only on the data publisher side.
Data Provision	Data provision mechanism (e.g. API) available, provide data to other stakeholders. Download (both data & metadata). Reference to the website of dataset.
Data quality	Metadata, Data Models, Licencing, RDF Compliance, Rating mechanisms
Legal Base Unit for the system	What is the central entity in the data model. E.g. the document.
Multilinguality in User Interface	In how many languages the UI is offered?
Multilinguality in Data	In how many languages the data are offered?
Analysis of datasets	Techniques that could be used for the analysis of datasets: Keywords extraction, semantic and thematic annotation, structural analysis of laws, correlations among legal artefacts, comparative analysis, Assessment of degree of transposition of an EU Directive in a National Legal Framework etc.
Visualisations	Visualisation techniques based on data analytics and legal informatics. E.g. Timeline analysis for all legal elements, visualising the progress and current status of a specific national or European legislation
Search functionalities	Supported Types of Search like titles and law number, parallel search in many EU member-state legal frameworks using simple keywords and multilingual search.
Navigation	Functionalities like Data overview (datasets); presentation of legal texts; geo-related navigation based on EU maps; Filters for optimization by country and legal body (passed_by) etc.; Keyword or thematic navigation.
Editing functionality	User profile creation. Support of creation and save of user's searches in laws. Editing capabilities on results. Extract search results.
Linking and combining data	How data from different or the same sources could be linked and/or combined. E.g. Aggregated Versions of laws in a specific timeframe; Showcase parliamentary data combined with law (draft-bill, bill, act (law) and public opinion data. Interrelation of laws and public opinion, including sentiment analysis.
Support and help	Support for users; Possibility to request data; support for providers.
Collaboration capabilities	Capabilities coming from the Web 2.0, like Discussion area for group collaboration, editing etc.

4. The complementarity of legal data platforms

Taking into account the requirements for legal data platforms and the requirements coming from the open data domain, as presented in the section 3, Table 2 contains the functionalities of the legal data platforms under investigation.

The framework for identifying characteristics of legal data platforms appears to be appropriate and useful, as it concentrates on all steps of the open data process as well as in the special characteristics of the legal informatics domain. The overview of characteristics of the legal data platforms indicates that there are many differences between the infrastructures. The analysed solutions offer different functionalities even in the search function that could be characterised as the main one. Different standards are used for the description of information and not advanced services are provided. The visualisation functionality restricts to the presentation of text in most of the cases. The analysis (comparison between laws and legal text lifetime) is also supported by limited solutions. All analysed platforms have their distinct functionalities as listed in Table 2. None of the platforms supports all aspects of the open data process nor the provision of advanced web 2.0 capabilities (rating, self-annotating, discussion).

The recognised differences in most of the aspects of the analysis framework suggest that these legal data platforms complement each other. This section summarises the identified functionalities of the legal data platforms. It categorises them into unique basic and advanced functionalities. Finally, in table 2 we discuss some open issues that occurred from the analysis providing also recommendations where possible. All the open issues and different ways of implementation could be seen as an opportunity to take advantage of the strengths of each infrastructure.

Table 2: Synthesis of functionalities for Legal Open Data Platforms and open issues

Type of Functionality	Analysis aspect	NOMOS-GR	RIS-AU	EURLEX-EU	Normativa-IT	DE	MANYLAWS	IUS-INFO	Open Issues and Recommendations
Basic Functionalities	Access and Acquisition	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	The most usable solutions in many cases are proprietary even for the basic functionality. All users should have access to high quality primary data supporting basic services. The connection to the primary source should be possible using an API. It is important to mention, that none of the platforms is utilising legal information drafting tools such LEOS to insure interoperability-by-design.
	Basic Search	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	The basic search should be done by title, year, number of LBU and keywords.
	Basic Navigation	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	Basic navigation should include thematic navigation.
	Data overview	X	X	X	X	X	✓	X	Data overview includes the basic visualisation of texts.
	Ability to download data & metadata	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Reference to the website of the source is also adequate.

	Support and Help	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	This includes functionality such as: possibility to request data in different types of format; support for users and providers; collaboration capabilities among users.	
	Coverage	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Most of the solutions target national data provision except Eur-Lex and ManyLaws. In some cases, the coverage could be also local depending on the national legal system.	
	Data Format	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	In most of the cases the basic data format is pdf. All primary data should be offered in a machine-processable format.	
	data type	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	The identified types of data are the following: bills, laws, case laws. The type of information might include a second level e.g. laws include presidential decrees and ministerial decisions as well. Bills may be distinguished in pre-bills. The level of granularity in terms of types of legal information may differ in each member state depending on the legal system.	
	Licencing	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Licencing seems to be followed by all solutions. An open data licence should be in place.	
	Data Model (ELI, AKN, Custom)	gr	au	eu	it	de	m	an	cr	Most of the platforms are using custom data models. Alignment and mapping of the legal information standards as well as mapping of custom data models to the basic ontologies. ELI is a flat and powerful metadata schema that maintains a lot of information about the documents. ELI also the AKN is a more sophisticated ontological approach enabling greater expressions and structural representation of legal texts. The analysed legal data platforms are aligned with either ELI or AKN or they are providing their data based on custom metadata schemata. Unlike ELI, AKN provides a structural representation for legal information. Each specific text fragment in official gazettes (article, paragraph etc.) could be expressed and described as such. One more issue is that AKN allows for the description of parliamentary data (i.e. bills information) enabling more thorough information for the history of laws as well as information relevant to citizens about who initiated and in some cases who voted for this specific bill/law.
	Legal System & Legal Base Unit for the platform	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	All analysed legal systems support the publication through the national gazette. In some cases the legal base unit might differ. For example the legal base unit of the RIS system in Austria is "section" even if the basic information is published in the national gazette. This is of course due to the fact that RIS provides advanced functionality in Austria, but this also constitutes a barrier towards the connection with other legal data sources/platforms.	
	Multilingualism in User Interface	X	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	X	Most of the analysed platforms in addition to national language also provide English versions of the UI.	
Advanced Functionalities	Multilingualism at the data level	X	X	✓	X	X	✓	X	This is necessary for the provision of advanced European-wide services.	
	Assessment of degree of transposition of an EU Directive in a National Legal Framework	X	X	X	X	X	✓	X	Translation services are needed.	
	Aggregated Consolidated Version in a specific period in time.	X	✓	X	X	X	✓	X	This service requires versioning of legal artifacts or update of the database in each publication of a new legal item.	
	Analyse and visualise public opinion	X	X	X	X	X	✓	X	E-consultation platforms are the sources of public opinion directly associated with bills or draft-bills. This source of information would capture the image of public opinion at the time of a bill or draft bill becoming a law. Usually, these platforms are accessed through their API services. Advanced analytics could be offered such as topics extraction, percentages of positive and negative opinions regarding each specific part of the bill. The acquired data is not stored in a pre-processing repository, but the processing is being an on-the-fly procedure.	

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	gr	au	eu	it	de	m an	cr	
Analysis of references to European Legislation by National Laws (graph visualisation) - national law to EU law.								
Comparative analysis of equivalent or relevant laws from different EU member states	X	X	X	X	X	✓	X	<p>In terms of advanced functionality, the semantic annotation and the adoption of advanced data models are necessary. In most of the cases, the semantic annotation (i.e. correlations among laws) procedure is performed by humans. The platforms provide functionality to specialists in order to analyse and find the related information that in turn allows for the provision of advanced services. Only recently have there been solutions that use the power of text mining and High-Performance Computing to analyse and annotate legal texts in an automatic manner. Even the most sophisticated systems, such as RIS in Austria, depend on the manpower to structure and annotate legal texts coming from government gazette. The following two semantic annotation approaches have been identified:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Analysing already published data: In most of the cases the government offers only plain text in the form of .pdf's. We noticed two ways of making legal information valuable for their users enabling semantic annotation and offering advanced services: (a) the human-related approach, in which legal experts acting as administrators provide the necessary information following a specific data model (in most of the cases custom) and (b) machine-related approach using advanced text mining techniques allowing the automated extraction and semantic annotation. 2. Drafting legislation in dedicated tools ensuring interoperability and conformance to standards. The next step to this endeavour is to incorporate a tool, like LEOS, in the drafting procedure in order to ensure the appropriate semantic annotation of legislation from the beginning. This way, text mining and machine learning techniques could only be used to offer really advanced services such as contradictions identification or even obligation extraction.
Comparative analysis of connected laws from the same member state	X	X	✓	✓	X	✓	X	
Interrelation of laws and public opinion, including sentiment analysis	X	X	X	X	X	✓	X	
Visualizations of correlations between different laws (graph visualisation)	X	X	X	X	X	✓	X	
Timeline analysis for all legal elements, visualising the progress and current status of a specific national or European legislation	X	X	X	X	X	✓	X	
Showcase parliamentary data (Parliaments data: draft-bill, bill, act (law))	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Advanced Search: Parallel search in many EU member-state legal frameworks using simple keywords	X	X	X	X	X	✓	X	
Advanced Search: Multilingual Search Service	X	X	✓	X	X	✓	X	
Advanced Navigation: Geo-related navigation based on maps. Filters for search optimisation by country and legal body.	X	✓	X	X	X	✓	X	
User dedicated profile. Uploading or relating information. Save user searches as well as editing on the results of the searches.	X	X	X	X	X	✓	X	This capability depends on the type of users the platform supports.

5. Discussion: towards a European legal information system

The European as well as the national legal systems are multi-layered and complex. Large quantities of legal documentation have been produced. A unique view on legal elements compounded by the fact that the number of legal documents being published online has grown exponentially. This is a direct consequence of advances in information technology and the increasing momentum of the Open Data movement in Europe and beyond. Nevertheless, pertinent legal information, embedded in large amounts of textual data available on the Internet, is also becoming increasingly difficult to find even for an expert user who cannot utilise text mining tools and techniques to extract data or meaning from large repositories.

Moreover, a knowledge of the information concerning the laws that apply within EU countries is considered of major importance in every-day or in mid- and long-term decision-making for various societal actors. Nowadays, the design and development of a European legal information system or the legal web is of paramount importance. This is due to the strategic goal of the EU to support the cross-country provision of services. In this background, the implementation of the EU legal web would be able to provide advanced legal services:

- to citizens: It would foster transparency and promote social inclusion of the law-making process. Citizens could find and understand relevant legislation, case law and other legal information and so that they understand how EU-law is created and implemented in different national settings. Citizens would be able to find information about real cases relevant for their everyday lives e.g. legislation and case law on studying abroad, or worker's rights and their protection in different countries.
- to public administrators: It would improve the quality of policy-making and law-drafting. A key constraint on contemporary policymakers, at both local and national level, is that they operate in an information scarce environment with only limited data on the current policy context or the effectiveness of proposed solutions. Therefore, for national and regional public administrators, it is crucial to have access to other countries or EU-legislation or even their existing national legal frameworks to facilitate learning, sharing best practices, but also better to underpin their own law-making by evidence from peers. For instance, the responsible legislative bodies or government law drafting offices would find it extremely helpful to be supported by legal information based services which would facilitate the fulfillment of the EU legislation requirements expressed by the EU directives, and help them to transpose these directives into national law.
- to businesses: It would enable the creation of a truly united EU-single market supported through services aiming at the strengthening of the economy. The facilitated comparison of the implementations of EU-law into national law are expected to increase the consistency of the various national implementations, one of the main benefits for SMEs and industries towards a truly single European market. For the economy, the aforementioned services would enable the establishment of cross-border activities because of easily accessible legal information in other member states. Easy access to different versions of laws as well as access to supplementary documents produced during the law-making processes, may clarify different national legal frameworks thus making it easier to assess the risk of a cross-border activity.

Based on our analysis, we identified two major constraints towards the implementation of the EU-wide legal information portal:

- **One interoperability standard to be followed for every type of legal information.** The existence of multiple standards for the description of legal information constitutes the first great barrier that needs to be addressed. Except the two main ontological approaches in the legal data domain (i.e. AKN and ELI), there are other approaches blur the landscape (Loutsaris & Charalabidis, 2020). ELI could be the standard for describing the legal documents as they are published from the national official publication offices, including the European Commission's Publication Office. The use of ELI has increased mostly because of its simplicity and its adoption by Eur-Lex. While AKN is a more descriptive standard that allows for structural descriptions of law and the provision of advanced services in the form of XML or RDF files, other approaches provide their own schemata.
- **Multilingual Support.** In order to support users of the legal web in their own language or at least in the English language, all national legal information should be translated. This effort will result in the duplication of legal information but also the creation of mutual understanding among all legal data actors, as well as in and staggered legal alignment across the EU. Eur-Lex is the first attempt to gather the European legislation in one place covering all languages of the EU. One key concept coming from the analysis of the legal data platforms is the measurement of the transposition degree of a European directive into each national legislation system. This would allow efficient monitoring from the side of the European Commission as well as it will serve as a means to member states for assessing or even following the paradigm of other countries' ways of transposition. The utilisation of the eTranslation DSI of the EC in order to offer (not formal) translations for the body of laws, is one of the most prominent solutions.

6. Conclusions

This study presented a framework for the analysis of legal data platforms functionalities and services. The framework was derived from the open data and the legal informatics domains. Our analysis showed that legal open data platforms are really diverse and each of these platforms provides different functionality and focuses on different aspects. All platforms have basic functionalities for acquiring and processing data at different levels of granularity depending on the national legal system, but all have their specific features to support the goals and intentions of the specific users of the platforms. Furthermore, our analysis proceeded to the assembly of all unique services and functionalities unveiling some open issues facing the design and development of the next generation of such platforms. A European approach and the semantic and multilingual barriers have been also discussed.

The differences in capabilities and functionalities of the legal open data platforms originate from the focus on different target groups. Different target groups have different needs in terms of types of legal data. The Austrian system which could be characterised as the most sophisticated national system proves itself to be very tricky for the implementation of the European-wide service: the creation of aggregated versions of laws around an issue for a specific timeframe. But, the supported service is mainly useful in Austria with a great degree of difficulty facing the possible replication and following the custom made data model. The ManyLaws platform offers the most advanced functionalities utilising the basic ontological approaches and could be the vehicle for legal data interoperability in the EU.

These differences in most of the aspects of the analysis framework suggest that these legal data platforms complement each other. All the open issues and different ways of implementation could be an opportunity to take advantage of the strengths of each infrastructure. In this way, an ecosystem around open legal data could be created in which different countries and actors are connected and can seemingly search and exchange information. Finally, it is of major importance to understand the specificities of each data type in terms of structure and semantic information as well as to finally follow one standard per data type.

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